

Accepted Manuscript

Identification of the key excreted molecule by *Lactobacillus fermentum* related to host iron absorption

Ana González, Natividad Gálvez, Jesús Martín, Fernando Reyes, Ignacio Pérez-Victoria, Jose M. Dominguez-Vera

PII: S0308-8146(17)30191-7

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2017.02.008>

Reference: FOCH 20561

To appear in: *Food Chemistry*

Received Date: 8 September 2016

Revised Date: 6 January 2017

Accepted Date: 1 February 2017

Please cite this article as: González, A., Gálvez, N., Martín, J., Reyes, F., Pérez-Victoria, I., Dominguez-Vera, J.M., Identification of the key excreted molecule by *Lactobacillus fermentum* related to host iron absorption, *Food Chemistry* (2017), doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2017.02.008>

This is a PDF file of an unedited manuscript that has been accepted for publication. As a service to our customers we are providing this early version of the manuscript. The manuscript will undergo copyediting, typesetting, and review of the resulting proof before it is published in its final form. Please note that during the production process errors may be discovered which could affect the content, and all legal disclaimers that apply to the journal pertain.

1 **Identification of the key excreted molecule by *Lactobacillus fermentum* related**
2 **to host iron absorption**

3 **Ana González¹, Natividad Gálvez¹, Jesús Martín², Fernando Reyes², Ignacio Pérez-**
4 **Victoria^{2,*}, Jose M. Dominguez-Vera^{1,*}**

5 ¹*Departamento de Química Inorgánica and Instituto de Biotecnología, Universidad de Granada,*
6 *18071 Granada, Spain. E-mail josema@ugr.es*

7 ²*Fundación MEDINA, Avda. del Conocimiento 34, 18016 Armilla, Granada, Spain*

8
9 **Abstract**

10 We have taken a vital step towards understanding why probiotic bacteria increase iron absorption
11 in the gastrointestinal tract. We show here that *Lactobacillus fermentum*, one of the main
12 probiotics of the microbiota, exhibits an extraordinary ferric-reducing activity. This activity is
13 predominantly due to an excreted molecule: *p*-hydroxyphenyllactic acid (HPLA). Reduction of
14 Fe(III) to Fe(II) is essential for iron absorption in the gastrointestinal tract. By reducing Fe(III),
15 HPLA boosts Fe(II) absorption through the DMT1 channels of enterocytes. An *in vitro*
16 experiment tested and confirmed this hypothesis. This discovery opens new avenues for the
17 treatment of iron deficiency in humans, one of the most common and widespread nutritional
18 disorders in the world.

19
20 **Keywords.** Iron metabolism, Probiotic bacteria, *Lactobacillus fermentum*, Iron supplement.

21

22

23 1. Introduction

24 Iron is an indispensable element for humans due to its involvement in essential biochemical
25 processes, including energy production, biosynthesis, replication, and locomotion (Crichton, 2001;
26 Silva & Faustino, 2015). Iron deficiency is the most common and widespread nutritional disorder
27 in the world. Besides affecting many children and women in developing countries, it is the only
28 nutrient deficiency prevalent in industrialized countries. The human body receives iron from food.
29 Though the daily requirement is 20-25 mg, no more than 2 mg are really absorbed (Milto et al.,
30 2016). Adequate iron levels in the blood are partially maintained by recycling the iron released
31 upon the degradation of iron-containing proteins, especially hemoglobin.

32 Heme-iron, present in hemoglobin and myoglobin, has high bioavailability (Huch & Schaefer
33 2006); however, the majority of iron in food (>90%) is in non-heme forms, either as free iron or
34 bound to low molecular-weight biomolecules (Crichton et al., 2008). Iron from food is mainly
35 absorbed by the duodenum enterocytes (90%). The stomach does not play a significant role in the
36 assimilation of iron, as its absorption is no more than 2% of the total (Shayeghi et al., 2005).

37 Iron transfer through the enterocyte membrane occurs by the combined activities of two proteins:
38 DMT1 and DcytB. The coupled work of DcytB/DMT1 is required for iron absorption since iron
39 enters the small intestine lumen mainly as Fe(III), the result of Fe(II) oxidation by gastric juice
40 components. Free Fe(III) is not able to enter into the enterocyte and must be reduced (McKie,
41 2008; Lane et al., 2015). The iron-regulated ferrireductase protein, DcytB, is highly expressed at
42 duodenal enterocytes and reduces Fe(III) to Fe(II). Upon reduction, Fe(II) is transferred across
43 the apical membrane of enterocytes by divalent metal transporters, mainly DMT1. Once inside the
44 enterocytes, Fe(II) can be used for synthesis of iron-containing proteins, transported to plasma by
45 the membrane protein ferroportin, or stored inside ferritin for later use when needed by cells

46 (McKie, 2008; Lane et al., 2015).

47 Interestingly, the bioavailability of iron is influenced by a series of chemical species in the
48 gastrointestinal tract. Whereas oxalates, phytates, phenolates and phosphates suppress iron
49 absorption, ascorbic and citric acids, increase it (Conrad & Umbreit, 2002). For this reason
50 commercial iron supplements are usually accompanied by ascorbic or citric acid. Strategies to
51 increase the intake of iron-rich foods, as well as dietary factors that enhance iron absorption, are
52 therefore extremely important for human health.

53 Probiotic bacteria constitute an important part of natural microbiota. Bacteria produce many
54 different metabolic substances that can act as antioxidants, bioflocculants or even immune
55 activators (Sommer & Bäckhed, 2013; Peccia & Kwan, 2016; Lin et al., 2014). They survive the
56 harsh stomach conditions and nest in different areas of intestines. Though the European Food
57 Safety Authority (EFSA) has recently concluded that there is insufficient evidence to claim that a
58 probiotic can help boost iron absorption (EFSA, 2016), other studies have shown that the
59 probiotic bacteria of the human gut microbiota facilitate iron absorption (Pérez-Conesa et al.,
60 2007; Hoppe et al., 2015; Bering et al., 2006). For example, it has been observed that the amount
61 of probiotic bacteria in gut flora is significantly lower in anemic patients than in healthy people.

62 The mechanisms of this influence are not entirely understood. As of yet no compound excreted by
63 bacteria has been shown to be related to iron absorption. Some have proposed that bacterial
64 fermentation in intestines decreases the pH due to the production of lactic acid, which can increase
65 iron solubility, leading to higher iron absorption (Hoppe et al., 2015). No published study has
66 evaluated the effect of the ferric-reducing activity of probiotic bacteria on iron absorption. We
67 show that *Lactobacillus fermentum*, one of the main components of the microbiota, exhibits
68 considerable extracellular ferric-reducing activity. We have isolated and identified the excreted

69 molecule that produces the ferric-reducing activity of *Lactobacillus fermentum*: *p*-
70 hydroxyphenyllactic acid (HPLA). This molecule efficiently reduces Fe(III) to Fe(II) at acidic pH.
71 From the results described here, we propose that the increase of iron absorption in humans, due to
72 the presence of probiotic bacteria in gut flora, could be related, not only to the decrease of pH
73 caused by these lactic acid bacteria (Hoppe et al., 2015), but also to the ferric-reducing activity of
74 the excreted HPLA. We have performed an *in vitro* experiment on iron uptake by enterocytes to
75 confirm that HPLA promotes iron absorption. These results shed light on the reason why probiotic
76 bacteria increase iron absorption in humans and can lead to more efficient strategies to increase
77 iron absorption in humans.

79 2. Materials and methods

80 2.1. *Lactobacillus fermentum* culture

81 *L. fermentum* CECT5716 was grown in anaerobic conditions in a synthetic medium at 37 °C with
82 orbital agitation for 24 h at an initial concentration of 1 mg of bacteria per ml of medium. The
83 synthetic medium consisted of (g l⁻¹) Na₂HPO₄ – 5.0, KH₂PO₄ – 6.0, trisammonium citrate – 2.0,
84 sucrose – 50.0, MgSO₄ – 1.0 and trace elements solution – 10 ml (consisting of (g l⁻¹): MnSO₄ –
85 2.0, CoCl₂ – 1.0, ZnCl₂ – 1.0 dissolved in 0.1 N HCl solution). The medium with an initial pH 6.7
86 was sterilized at 121 °C. The final *L. fermentum* cell concentration was 3.3x10⁸ CFU ml⁻¹.

87 2.2. Ferric-reducing activity of *L. fermentum*

88 1 ml of bacterial culture was mixed with 3.6 µl of a 10 mM Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O water solution and 7
89 µl of a 70 mM 3-(2-pyridiyl)-5,6-diphenyl-1,2,4-triazine-*p,p'*-disulfonic acid monosodium salt
90 hydrate (ferrozine, fz) water solution and the resulting mixture was incubated for 6 and 24 h and
91 then centrifuged. The ferric-reducing capacity of *L. fermentum* was measured by UV-vis

92 spectroscopy through the apparition of a band centred at 562 nm due to the formation of the
93 complex $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{fz})_3]$ ($\epsilon^{562} = 27,900 \text{ M}^{-1}$). A control of the ferric-reducing activity of the culture
94 media, without bacteria, showed no UV-vis band at 562 nm. Similar ferric-reducing activity was
95 exhibited by the corresponding supernatant solution (1 ml) from the bacterial culture.

96 *2.3. Isolation of excreted bacterial compound/s with ferric-reducing activity*

97 Bacteria were removed by centrifugation at 3000 g for 10 min and then the supernatant was
98 filtered, using EMD Millipore Steritop™ Sterile Vacuum Bottle-Top Filters. 2 l of the filtered
99 supernatant solution were subjected to solid-phase extraction on a column packed with SP-207ss
100 brominated polystyrenic resin (65 g to render a column bed of 3.5 cm diameter and 11 cm height)
101 previously equilibrated with water. The column was washed with water (1 l) and afterwards eluted
102 with 200 ml of methanol. The solvent was evaporated under a nitrogen stream and the resulting
103 extract dissolved in 500 μl of DMSO and further purified by reversed phase semi-preparative
104 HPLC (Agilent Zorbax SB-C8, $9.4 \times 250 \text{ mm}$, $7 \mu\text{m}$; 3.6 ml/min , UV detection at 210 and 280
105 nm) with a linear gradient of water- CH_3CN (5% to 50%) over 40 min to yield 80 fractions of 1.8
106 ml. The ferric-reducing activity of each fraction was tested, using a 96-well microtitre plate
107 containing 2 μl of each fraction diluted with 198 μl of water. 1.08 μl of a 10 mM $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ stock
108 solution and 2.1 μl of a 70 mM fz stock solution were added to each well. The presence of the
109 complex $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{fz})_3]$, determined by measuring the absorbance at 570 nm, using a microplate reader
110 (Envision 2104 multilabel reader, Perkin Elmer), was detected only in fractions 8 to 11. These
111 fractions were pooled, evaporated and then dissolved in 1 ml of distilled water. The resulting
112 water solution was further purified by reversed phase semi-preparative HPLC (Waters Atlantis
113 C18, $9.4 \times 250 \text{ mm}$, $7 \mu\text{m}$; 3.6 ml/min , UV detection at 210 and 280 nm) with a linear gradient of
114 water- CH_3CN (0 to 25%) over 40 min to yield 80 fractions of 1.8 ml. The ferric-reducing activity

115 of these fractions was tested as before. Only fractions 28 and 29 exhibited ferric-reducing activity.
116 These fractions were pooled, evaporated and analyzed by LC-ESI-TOFMS and NMR
117 spectroscopy.

118 2.4. Structure elucidation of the excreted bacterial compound with ferric-reducing activity

119 For NMR analysis, the sample (pooled dry fractions or the HPLA standard) was dissolved in
120 deuterated methanol, CD₃OD. NMR spectra, including ¹H, COSY, HSQC and HMBC, were
121 recorded on a Bruker Avance III spectrometer (500 and 125 MHz for ¹H and ¹³C NMR,
122 respectively) equipped with a 1.7 mm TCI MicroCryoProbe™, using the signal of the residual
123 deuterated solvent as internal reference (δ_{H} 3.31 and δ_{C} 49.0 ppm). LC-DAD-ESI-HRMS analysis
124 of an aliquot of the final pooled fractions was performed on an Agilent 1200 rapid resolution
125 HPLC system hyphenated with a Bruker maXis QTOF mass spectrometer, using a Zorbax SB-C8
126 column (2.1 × 30 mm, 5 μm), maintained at 40 °C and with a flow rate of 300 μl min⁻¹. Solvent A
127 consisted of 10% acetonitrile and 90% water with 1.3 mM trifluoroacetic acid and ammonium
128 formate, and solvent B was 90% acetonitrile and 10% water with 1.3 mM trifluoroacetic acid and
129 ammonium formate. The gradient started at 10% B and went to 100% B in 6 minutes, kept at
130 100% B for 2 minutes and returned to 10 % B for 2 min to initialize the system. Full diode array
131 UV scans from 100 to 900 nm were collected in 4 nm steps at 0.25 s/scan. The mass spectrometer
132 was operated in positive ESI mode. The instrumental parameters were: 4 kV capillary voltage,
133 drying gas flow of 11 l min⁻¹ at 200 °C, nebulizer pressure at 2.8 bars. TFA-Na cluster ions were
134 used for mass calibration of the instrument prior to sample injection. Pre-run calibration was by
135 infusion with the same TFA-Na calibrant. The structure of the target compound was established,
136 using the NMR data. Its molecular formula was corroborated by the HRMS results. Further
137 confirmation on the identity was obtained by direct comparison with the ¹H and HSQC NMR

138 spectra of an HPLA standard prepared in CD₃OD. The corresponding test of ferric-reducing
139 activity of the HPLA standard unequivocally determined this molecule as the target excreted
140 compound responsible for such reducing power displayed by the *L. fermentum* culture.

141 2.5. Ferric-reducing activity of HPLA vs pH

142 Racemic HPLA was acquired from Sigma-Aldrich. Solutions of HPLA (144 μM) were prepared in
143 different buffers with pH ranging from 3.0 to 7.4 and mixed with solutions of 10 mM
144 Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O and 70 mM of fz. Ferric-reducing activity of HPLA at these different pH values
145 was measured by UV-vis spectroscopy through the appearance of a band centred at 562 nm, due
146 the formation of the complex [Fe^{II}(fz)₃] (ε⁵⁶²= 27,900 M⁻¹). The results showed that HPLA
147 exhibits high ferric-reducing activity only at low pH.

148 2.6. Ferric-reducing activity of *L. fermentum* after HPLA addition

149 The ferric-reducing capacity of *L. fermentum* was measured, as indicated above, after incubation
150 for 6 and 24 h. HPLA (3.6 μM) was added to the supernatant obtained after centrifugation of the
151 6 h culture and the ferric-reducing activity of the resulting mixture was measured. The ferric-
152 reducing activity of HPLA (3.6 μM) in the medium grown was used as control.

153 2.7. Ferric-reducing activity of HPLA versus lactic acid (LA), *p*-methylphenol (*p*-mPh) and the 154 mixture *p*-methylphenol and lactic acid (LA+*p*-mPh)

155 Two different experimental conditions were assayed, excess and deficiency of Fe(III) with respect
156 to the reducing molecules. The ferric-reducing activity was referred to the initial concentrations of
157 Fe(III) or the chemical reductant, respectively.

158 A 50 mM stock solution of HPLA was prepared by dissolving 9.1 mg in 1 ml of Mili-Q water.
159 Solutions of LA and *p*-mPh at the same 50 mM concentration were prepared, as well as a mixture
160 solution of both (LA+*p*-mPh) containing 50 mM of each reducing molecule. Lactic acid and *p*-

161 methylphenol were also purchased from Sigma-Aldrich.
162 110 μl of each stock solution were added to 879 μl of Mili-Q water containing 3.6 μl of a 10 mM
163 solution of $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 7 μl of a ferrozine solution (70 mM). The *p*-methylphenol and
164 lactic acid mixture was preparing by adding 110 μl of the *p*-methylphenol stock solution and 110
165 μl of the lactic acid stock solution to 769 μl of Mili-Q water containing 3.6 μl of a 10 mM
166 $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution and 7 l of a 70 mM fz solution. The final concentrations of the reducing
167 molecules and Fe(III) were 5.5 mM and 36 μM . The ferric-reducing activity of each sample was
168 determined at 0, 2, 4 and 24 h by monitoring the UV-vis band at 562 nm of the complex
169 $[[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{fz})_3]$. In a second experiment a 25 μM concentration of each reducing molecule was used.

170 2.8. *In vitro* experiment on iron internalization in enterocyte cells

171 IEC6 epithelial rat small intestine cells were provided by the Scientific Instrumentation Centre
172 (University of Granada, Spain). Cell line was grown adherently and maintained in DMEM + 2mM
173 glutamine + 0.1 IU/ml of insulin + 5% of foetal bovine serum (FBS) at 37 °C in 5% CO_2 . All
174 experiments were performed in 12-well plates. Cells were seeded onto the plates at a density of 5
175 $\times 10^4$ cells per well and incubated for 48 h prior to the experiments.

176 The wells were filled up to a final volume of 1ml with a water solution of $\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (360
177 μM), the grown medium and HPLA, at two different concentrations, 360 and 36 μM . Two more
178 wells with a blank sample containing only cells were also prepared. Plates were incubated at 37°C
179 for 0.5 or 5 h. Samples were filtered, using a 0.2 μm Minisart RC filter and the total iron
180 concentration (Fe(II) and Fe(III)) measured by ICP-OES.

181 2.9. Statistical analysis

182 The ferric-reducing activity of HPLA versus LA, *p*-mPh and the mixture LA+*p*-mPh and the *in*
183 *vitro* experiment on iron internalization in enterocyte cells were conducted in triplicates.

184 Descriptive error bars represent the standard deviation (SD) of the triplicates and it was calculated
185 using the n-1 method.

186

187 **3. Results and discussion**

188 *3.1. Lactobacillus fermentum shows a high ferric-reducing activity*

189 The ability to reduce Fe(III) to Fe(II) is usually related to the antioxidant properties of a chemical
190 species. In the context of iron metabolism, this redox reaction is essential for iron absorption since
191 non-heme iron is usually in the form of Fe(III), which cannot be absorbed by enterocytes until it
192 has been reduced to Fe(II).

193 The ferric-reducing activity of *L. fermentum* was measured through its incubation with Fe(III) and
194 ferrozine by monitoring the formation of the Fe(II) complex with the chelator, $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{fz})_3]$, through
195 the appearance and increase of its characteristic UV-vis band at 562 nm. The supernatant liquid
196 isolated after centrifugation of the bacteria exhibits activity similar to that of the bacterial broth
197 after 6 and 24 h (Figure 1). This evidence indicates that the ferric-reducing ability of *L. fermentum*
198 is due to the molecule(s) excreted by the bacteria. However, the patterns of ferric-reducing activity
199 of the supernatant and the bacterial culture differ. Whereas the former is able to reduce a specific
200 amount of Fe(III) and then is rendered inactive, the latter exhibits prolonged activity. The bacterial
201 culture can reduce additional amounts of Fe(III) after reducing the same amount of Fe(III) as
202 reduced by the supernatant. This could be explained if the bacterium continuously excreted or
203 regenerated the molecule responsible for its ferric-reducing activity.

204
 205 Figure 1. Ferric-reducing activity of *L. Fermentum* (red) and the supernatant liquid (blue) after 6
 206 (dashed lines) and 24 h. Development of the UV-vis band centred at 562 nm due to $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{fz})_3]$
 207 shows the ferric-reducing activity.

208
 209 The characterization of excreted active molecules by living organisms is of great interest in the
 210 biomedical field. In fact, some of these molecules are in the pharmaceutical market for different
 211 medical purposes. We addressed the challenge of isolating and characterizing the molecule
 212 responsible for the ferric-reducing activity of *L. fermentum* because no such study has been thus
 213 far done.

214 An assay-guided fractionation approach was implemented. First, an extract of the culture
 215 supernatant was prepared. A brominated polystyrenic resin (SP207ss), with the capacity to retain
 216 both polar and non-polar compounds, was used for the solid-phase. After confirming the ferric-
 217 reducing activity of the extract obtained by elution from the resin with methanol, the extract was
 218 subjected to semipreparative HPLC fractionation. After passing through a C8 reversed-phase
 219 column, the fractions with the reducing ability were pooled and further fractionated with a C18
 220 column. The two fractions showing ferric-reducing activity were pooled and analyzed by NMR

221 and LC-DAD-ESI-TOFMS. The ^1H NMR spectrum (Figure 2) revealed a mixture of a few
222 compounds. The signals of a *para*-hydroxyphenyl group, corresponding to one of the major
223 components, could easily be identified. Additional 2D NMR experiments, including COSY, HSQC
224 and HMBC (supporting information S1-S8), were employed to elucidate the connectivity of the
225 compound containing this structural moiety, which turned out to correspond to *p*-
226 hydroxyphenyllactic acid (HPLA, Chart 1).

227

228

229

Chart 1. Chemical structure of *p*-hydroxyphenyllactic acid HPLA.

230

231

232 Figure 2. ^1H NMR spectra (500 MHz, CD_3OD) of the final pooled fractions displaying ferric-
233 reducing activity (red) and *p*-hydroxyphenyllactic acid standard, HPLA (blue).

234

235 The molecular formula of HPLA, $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$, was a major component detected in the corresponding
236 LC-HRMS analysis (Supporting Information S9).

237 Further confirmation of the identity of the compound was obtained by direct comparison of the

238 NMR spectra of the final pooled active fractions with the spectrum of a commercial HPLA
239 standard (Figure 2). When the standard was evaluated for its ferric-reducing activity, it showed the
240 same reducing power. Thus, HPLA is the compound excreted by *L. fermentum*, responsible for
241 the bacterial ferric-reducing activity.

242 Interestingly, HPLA has already been identified as an antioxidant compound, in a radical-
243 scavenging assay, produced by the sister species *Lactobacillus plantarum* (Suzuki et al., 2013).

244 The production of HPLA by lactic acid bacteria (LAB) was first reported from *L. plantarum* 21B
245 (Lavermicocca et al., 2000). This compound has shown antifungal activity and contributes to the

246 biopreservative properties claimed for LAB (Crowley et al., 2013). HPLA has been isolated as its
247 L- enantiomer in *L. plantarum* (Suzuki et al., 2013). The same chirality is expected for the HPLA

248 produced by the *L. fermentum* strain employed in this work, assuming a common pathway for
249 HPLA production among lactobacilli. The biosynthesis of HPLA in LAB likewise explains the

250 apparent regeneration of the ferric-reducing activity observed for *L. fermentum* in reduction
251 experiments with increasing amounts of Fe(III). In these bacteria, tyrosine is transformed by

252 transamination into 4-hydroxyphenylpyruvate, which is further reduced to HPLA by a hydroxyacid
253 dehydrogenase (Lavermicocca et al., 2000; Valerio et al., 2004; Li et al., 2007). Transamination is

254 the rate-limiting step in such biosynthesis. It has been demonstrated that HPLA production
255 dramatically increases in fermentations of *Lactobacillus sp. SK007* supplemented with 4-

256 hydroxyphenylpyruvate (tyrosine as supplement renders just a moderate increase in production)
257 (Mu et al., 2010). These results indicate that the bacterium is very efficient in reducing 4-

258 hydroxyphenylpyruvate to HPLA. Such efficiency would help to recycle the HPLA consumed in
259 the reduction of Fe(III). In this ferrereduction HPLA gets oxidized to 4-hydroxyphenylpyruvate

260 which would get back to HPLA via the corresponding *Lactobacillus* hydroxyacid dehydrogenase,

261 that way explaining the apparent regeneration of the ferric-reducing activity already mentioned.
 262 Once HPLA was identified as the molecule responsible for the ferric-reducing activity of *L.*
 263 *fermentum*, a study of its ability to reduce Fe(III) to Fe(II) as a function of pH was carried out. As
 264 shown in Figure 3, HPLA exhibits a ferric-reducing activity extremely dependent on pH. At pH
 265 above 6, HPLA hardly reduces Fe(III) to Fe(II) but, at pH 3.8, this reduction is practically
 266 complete.

267

268

269

270

271

272

273

274 Figure 3. Ferric-reducing activity of HPLA at different pHs and buffers. The % of Fe(III)
 275 reduction was calculated as the ratio between concentrations of $[\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{fz})_3]$ and the initial Fe(III).

276

277 To further verify that HPLA is the principal factor in the ferric-reducing activity of *L. fermentum*,
 278 we performed an experiment in which HPLA was directly added to a 6 h bacterial culture. The
 279 resulting ferric-reducing activity of the mixture was compared to that of the 24 h bacterial culture.

280 As shown in Figure 4, the addition of HPLA to the culture media leads to an increase in the ferric-
 281 reducing activity (Figure 4, green bar). The activity of this mixture is close to the sum of that of *L.*
 282 *fermentum* (Figure 4, blue bar) and the HPLA control (Figure 4, red bar). Likewise, the addition
 283 of HPLA to the 6 h culture medium gives rise to a ferric-reducing activity close to that of the 24 h

284 culture medium, indicating that HPLA is continuously excreted during the bacterial growth from 6
285 to 24 h and that this molecule is responsible for the ferric-reducing activity of *L. fermentum*.

286

287

288 Figure 4. Ferric-reducing activity, as a percentage of Fe(III) reduction, of a 6 and 24 h culture of
289 *L. fermentum* (blue), the addition of HPLA (3,6 μM) to the culture medium (green), and HPLA at
290 the same concentration in the growth medium (red).

291 Interestingly, HPLA seems to be a specific reductant of Fe(III). It does not reduce other chemical
292 species, such as Au(III) or the polyoxometalate $[\text{P}_2\text{Mo}^{\text{VI}}_{18}\text{O}_{62}]^{6-}$, which are quite reduced in the
293 presence of *L. fermentum* (Carmona et al., 2014; Gonzalez et al., 2015). This result indicates that
294 the chemical reducing mechanism of *L. fermentum* does not solely contain HPLA but also other
295 reducing molecules. Our work has reached a milestone in unravelling such a reducing mechanism
296 after having being able to identify one of the molecules excreted by *L. fermentum* and label its
297 functionality for future applications.

298 The characterization of HPLA as the main agent of the pH-dependent ferric-reducing activity of *L.*
299 *fermentum* and its strong reducing ability dependence on pH, provokes us to hypothesise that
300 excreted HPLA could reduce Fe(III) under acid stomach conditions and facilitate Fe(II)
301 absorption in the duodenum, as occurs for ascorbic and citric acids. Related studies report that

302 low molecular weight fractions exhibiting ferric-reducing activity in human milk enhance iron
303 absorption in newborns (Pullakhandama et al., 2007).

304 HPLA contains two chemical moieties with potential reducing Fe(III) activity: the terminal lactic
305 acid and the phenol group. To get insight into the mechanism of the ferric-reducing activity of
306 HPLA, we compared the HPLA ability to reduce Fe(III) at acidic pH with that of its pure chemical
307 moieties, namely lactic acid (LA) and *p*-methylphenol (*p*-mPh), and the mixture of both (LA + *p*-
308 mPh). Both an excess of reducing molecules with respect to Fe(III) and a slight excess of Fe(III)
309 with respect to the active molecules were examined. The first was to understand the kinetics of
310 Fe(III) reduction and the second was to evaluate the ferric-reducing activity of the individual
311 chemical moieties.

312 The most interesting result of these experiments is that HPLA reduces Fe(III) to the same extent
313 as the mixture of lactic acid and *p*-mPh, practically doubling the reducing capacity of separated LA
314 and *p*-mPh (Figure 5). Thus, both HPLA chemical moieties are effective for Fe(III) reduction and
315 exhibit ferric-reducing activity. When the experiment was done in excess of Fe(III) towards the
316 reducing molecules, the ferric-reducing activity vs. time revealed that HPLA seems to reduce
317 Fe(III), first by the LA moiety and then by *p*-mPh (Figure 5A). Fe(III) reduction versus time
318 shows that the reduction by HPLA follows the same pattern as LA in the initial steps. The
319 %Fe(III) reduction was about 20% by HPLA and 15% by LA after 2h, whereas that of *p*-mPh was
320 90%. This indicates that pure *p*-mPh has faster Fe(III) reduction mechanisms than LA and HPLA.
321 However, over a prolonged period of time (24 h), the %Fe(III) reductions of HPLA, *p*-mPh, and
322 the mixture, LA- *p*-mPh, are similar and close to 100%, whereas that of LA is about 80%.

323 In the second experiment, Fe(III) was in excess with respect to the reducing molecules. The
324 results clearly indicate that the capacity of HPLA to reduce Fe(III) is double than that of LA and

325 of *p*-mPh and is close to the capacity of the mixture of both (Figure 5B). Therefore, the
 326 combination of both chemical moieties (lactic acid and phenol) makes HPLA an extraordinary
 327 Fe(III) reducing molecule.

328

329
 330
 331 Figure 5. Ferric-reducing activity at pH 3.5 of HPLA, lactic acid (LA), *p*-methylphenol (*p*-mPh)
 332 and the mixture of LA and *p*-mPh at different times. A: Fe(III) is in default with respect to
 333 reducing molecules. B: Fe(III) is in excess with respect to the reducing molecules. The %Fe(III)
 334 reduction is referred to the concentration of Fe(III) (A) or the reducing molecules (B). Error bars,
 335 ±SD.

336
 337 An *in vitro* experiment of iron uptake by enterocytes in the presence of HPLA was performed to
 338 test whether HPLA could be related to the effect on iron absorption by probiotic bacteria, (Figure

339 6). HPLA was incubated at two concentrations (36 and 360 μM) with enterocytes (IEC-6 cells) in
 340 the presence of Fe(III). *L. fermentum*, and its supernatant liquid obtained after bacterial
 341 centrifugation, were also incubated with IEC-6 enterocytes and Fe(III). The concentration of total
 342 iron (Fe(II) and Fe(III)) of the solutions was measured at two different times (30 and 300 min), by
 343 ICP-OES, to evaluate the amount of iron internalized into the cells.

344
 345 Figure 6. Fe(III) (367 μM) was incubated with enterocyte cells IEC-6 in the presence of HPLA at
 346 36 μM (columns 3), 360 μM (columns 4), *L. fermentum* (columns 5) and the supernatant liquid
 347 obtained after centrifugation of *L. fermentum* (columns 6). Fe concentrations in the solutions were
 348 measured by ICP-OES after 30 (orange) and 300 min (red). Columns 1 correspond to the initial
 349 Fe(III) solutions; columns 2 correspond to Fe(III) after incubation with IEC-6 (control) and
 350 columns 7 data to the plates only containing cells (control). Error bars, $\pm\text{SD}$.

351
 352 The first conclusion drawn from these data is that *L. fermentum* and its supernatant liquid
 353 significantly increased iron absorption by enterocytes. Values for Fe(III) absorption after
 354 incubation with enterocytes are very close to initial values, meaning that enterocytes hardly absorb

355 Fe(III) (Figure 6). In contrast, both enterocytes with *L. fermentum* and enterocytes with the
356 supernatant (the excreted molecules) reduce iron concentrations to less than half those of the
357 controls. Thus, the bacteria and excreted molecules facilitate enterocyte iron uptake. Moreover,
358 enterocyte iron absorption by bacteria and by supernatant liquid obtained after centrifugation are
359 similar, which substantiates that the effect of probiotic bacteria on iron absorption is due to the
360 molecules excreted by these bacteria.

361 HPLA is less effective in assisting enterocytes with iron absorption than the bacterial broth or its
362 supernatant liquid. However, higher HPLA concentrations (360 μM) result in more absorption.
363 Iron concentrations decrease from approximately 350 μM (Figure 6, columns 2) to 231 and 211
364 μM after 30 and 300 min of incubation, respectively. While the higher concentration of HPLA
365 (360 μM) increases enterocyte iron uptake by about 40%, the increase for the lower HPLA
366 concentration (36 μM) is only about 30%.

367 Though HPLA clearly increases enterocyte iron absorption, the higher quantities of enterocyte
368 iron absorption by *L. fermentum* and its supernatant liquid with respect to HPLA suggest that
369 other molecules excreted by the probiotic bacteria must also be involved in this complex process.
370 Lactic acid is a likely candidate, since *L. fermentum* is defined as a lactic bacterium that excretes
371 this molecule while proliferating.

372 Therefore, HPLA exhibits extraordinary ferric-reducing activity and increases enterocyte iron
373 uptake. Taking into account enterocytes in the duodenum and the participation of the ferric-
374 reducing protein DcytB (McKie, 2008; Lane et al., 2015), our results point to a mechanism of iron
375 absorption in which HPLA would act similarly to DcytB by facilitating Fe(III) reduction in the
376 stomach and ultimately promoting Fe(II) uptake by DMT1 channels.

377 **4. Conclusions**

378 *L. fermentum*, one of the main probiotics of the microbiota, exhibits an extraordinary ferric-
379 reducing activity. This activity is mainly due to one of the molecules excreted by this bacterium: *p*-
380 hydroxyphenyllactic acid (HPLA). HPLA effectively reduces Fe(III) to Fe(II) and in the
381 gastrointestinal tract can mimic the functionality of the DcytB ferric-reducing protein by
382 promoting iron uptake by enterocytes. We have demonstrated that the increase of iron absorption in
383 the presence of probiotic bacteria is related to the ferric-reducing activity of excreted molecules.
384 These results are a huge step towards solving the enigma of why probiotic bacteria increase iron
385 absorption. This discovery opens new avenues for the treatment of human iron deficiency, one of
386 the most common and widespread nutritional disorders in the world.

387

388 **Supporting Information**

389 Figure S1-S8. ¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CD₃OD) of the final pooled fractions displaying
390 ferric-reducing activity. Comparison of the ¹H NMR spectra of the final pooled fractions
391 displaying ferric-reducing activity and the HPLA standard. COSY spectrum of the final pooled
392 fractions displaying ferric-reducing activity showing the key correlations for HPLA. HSQC
393 spectrum of the final pooled fractions displaying ferric-reducing activity. HSQC spectrum of the
394 HPLA standard. HMBC spectrum of the final pooled fractions displaying ferric-reducing activity
395 showing the key correlations for HPLA.

396 Table S1. NMR spectroscopic data (500 MHz, CD₃OD, at 24 °C) for HPLA.

397 Figure S9. LC-UV-HRMS analysis of the final pooled fractions displaying ferric-reducing activity
398 showing detection of a major component matching the molecular formula of HPLA.

399 **Acknowledgements**

400 This work was funded by MINECO and FEDER (project CTQ2015-64538-R) and Biosearch S.A.
401 (CARMENTA Project-FEDER INTERCONECTA). The HPLC and NMR equipment used in this
402 work were acquired via grants for scientific and technological infrastructures from the Ministerio
403 de Ciencia e Innovación [Grants No. PCT-010000-2010-4 (NMR) and INP-2011-0016-PCT-
404 010000-ACT6 (HPLC)].

405

406

407 **References**

408 Bansal, V., Bharde, A., Ramanathan, R., & Bhargava, S. K. (2012). Inorganic materials using
409 'unusual' microorganisms. *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science*, 179–182, 150-168.

410 Bering, S., Suchdev, S., & Sjolto, L. (2006). A lactic acidfermented oat gruel increases non-
411 haem iron absorption from a phytate-rich meal in healthy women of childbearing age.
412 *British Journal of Nutrition*, 96(1), 80-85.

413 Carmona, F., Martin, M., Galvez, N., & Dominguez-Vera, J. M. (2014). Bioinspired magneto-
414 optical bacteria. *Inorganic Chemistry*, 53(16), 8565-8569.

415 Conrad, M., & Umbreit, J. (2002). Pathways of iron absorption. *Blood Cells, Molecules, and*
416 *Diseases*, 29(3), 336-355.

417 Crichton, R. (2001). *Inorganic Biochemistry of Iron Metabolism: from Molecular Mechanisms to*
418 *Clinical Consequences*. England: John Wiley & Sons.

419 Crichton, R., Danielson, B., & Geisser, P. (2008). *Iron Therapy with Special Emphasis on*
420 *Intravenous Administration* (4th ed.). London-Boston: International Medical Publishers.

- 421 Crowley, S., Mahonya, J., & Sinderen D. V. (2013). Current perspectives on antifungal lactic acid
422 bacteria as natural bio-preservatives. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 33(2), 93-
423 109.
- 424 EFSA Panel on Dietetic Products and Allergies (NDA). (2016). *Scientific Opinion on Dietary*
425 *Reference Values for vitamin D*. European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), 4550-4829.
- 426 González, A., Gálvez, N., Clemente-León, M., & Domínguez-Vera, J. M. (2015). Electrochromic
427 polyoxometalate material as a sensor of bacterial activity. *Chemical Communications*, 51,
428 10119-10122.
- 429 Hoppe, M., Onning, G., Berggren, A., & Hulthen, L. (2015). Probiotic strain *Lactobacillus*
430 *plantarum* 299v increases iron absorption from an iron-supplemented fruit drink: a double-
431 isotope cross-over single-blind study in women of reproductive age. *British Journal of*
432 *Nutrition*, 114(8), 1195-1202.
- 433 Huch, R., & Schaefer, R. (2006). *Iron Deficiency and Iron Deficiency Anaemia. Pocket Atl.* (pp.
434 1-70). New York: Thieme Medical Publishers.
- 435 Lane, D. J., Bae, D. H., Merlot, A. M., Sahni, S., & Richardson, D. R. (2015). Duodenal
436 cytochrome b (DCYTB) in iron metabolism: an update on function and regulation.
437 *Nutrients*, 7(4), 2274-2296.
- 438 Lavermicocca, P., Valerio, F., Evidente, A., Lazzaroni, S., Corsetti, A., & Gobetti, M. (2000).
439 Purification and Characterization of Novel Antifungal Compounds from the Sourdough
440 *Lactobacillus plantarum* Strain 21B. *Applied and Environmental Microbiology*, 66(9),
441 4084-4090.
- 442 Li, X., Jiang, B., & Pan, B. (2007). Biotransformation of phenylpyruvic acid to phenyllactic acid
443 by growing and resting cells of a *Lactobacillus* sp. *Biotechnology Letters*, 29(4), 593-597.

- 444 Lin, C. S., Chang, C. J., Lu, C. C., Martel, J., Ojcius, D. M., Ko, Y. F., Young, J. D., & Lai, H. C.
445 (2014). Impact of the gut microbiota, prebiotics, and probiotics on human health and
446 disease. *Biomedical Journal*, *37*(5), 259-268.
- 447 McKie, A. T. (2008). The role of Dcytb in iron metabolism: an update. *Biochemical Society*
448 *Transactions*, *36*(6), 1239-1241.
- 449 Milto, I.V., Suhodolo, I. V., Prokopieva, V. D., & Klimenteva, T. K. (2016). Molecular and
450 cellular bases of iron metabolism in humans. *Biochemistry*, *81*(6), 549-564.
- 451 Mu, W., Yang, Y., Jia, J., Zhang, T., & Jiang, B. (2010). Production of 4-hydroxyphenyllactic
452 acid by *Lactobacillus* sp. SK007 fermentation. *Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering*,
453 *109*(4), 369-371.
- 454 Peccia, J., & Kwan, S. E. (2016). Buildings, Beneficial Microbes, and Health. *Trends in*
455 *Microbiology*, *24*(8), 595-597.
- 456 Perez-Conesa, D., Lopez, G., & Ros, G. (2007). Effect of Probiotic, Prebiotic and Synbiotic
457 Follow-up Infant Formulas on Iron Bioavailability in Rats. *Food Science and Technology*
458 *International*, *13*(1), 69-77.
- 459 Pullakhandama, R., Krishnapillai, M. N., Kasulab, S., Kilaria, S., & Thippandea, T. G. (2008).
460 Ferric reductase activity of low molecular weight human milk fraction is associated with
461 enhanced iron solubility and uptake in Caco-2 cells. *Biochemical and Biophysical*
462 *Research Communications*, *374*, 369-372.
- 463 Shayeghi, M., Latunde-Dada, G. O., Oakhill, J. S., Laftah, A. H., Takeuchi, K., Halliday, N.,
464 Khan, Y., Warley, A., McCann, F. E., Hider, R. C., Frazer, D. M., Anderson, G. J., Vulpe,
465 C. D., Simpson, R. J., & McKie, A. T. (2005). Identification of an intestinal heme
466 transporter. *Cell*, *122*(5), 789-801.

- 467 Silva, B., & Faustino, P. (2015). An overview of molecular basis of iron metabolism regulation
468 and the associated pathologies. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta*, 1852(7), 1347-1359.
- 469 Sommer, F., & Backhed, F. (2013). The gut microbiota--masters of host development and
470 physiology. *Nature Reviews Microbiology*, 11(4), 227-238.
- 471 Suzuki, Y., Kosaka, M., Shindo, K., Kawasumi, T., Kimoto-Nira, H., & Suzuki, C. (2013).
472 Identification of antioxidants produced by *Lactobacillus plantarum*. *Bioscience,*
473 *Biotechnology, and Biochemistry*, 77(6), 1299-1302.
- 474 Valerio, F., Lavermicocca, P., Pascale, M., & Visconti, A. (2004). Production of phenyllactic acid
475 by lactic acid bacteria: an approach to the selection of strains contributing to food quality
476 and preservation. *FEMS Microbiology Letters*, 233(2), 289-295.
- 477 World Health Organization. World Health Statistics 2016: Monitoring health for the SDGs.
478 (2016). <http://www.who.int/nutrition/topics/ida/en/> Accessed 08.09.16

479

480

481

482 **Graphical Contents**483 **Identification of the Key Excreted Molecule Related to Host Iron Absorption**

484 **Ana González, Natividad Gálvez, Jesús Martín, Fernando Reyes, Ignacio Pérez-Victoria,**
485 **Jose M. Dominguez-Vera**

486
487 Probiotic bacteria increase iron absorption in humans due to their ferric-reducing activity. One of

488 these bacteria, *Lactobacillus fermentum* excretes HPLA, which reduces Fe(III) to Fe(II). This

489 Fe(II) is subsequently internalized into enterocytes by DMT1.

490

491

492

493
494
495
496 Iron deficiency is one of the most common and widespread nutritional disorders in the world.
497 Two billion people, over 30% of the world's population, are anemic, mainly due to iron
498 deficiency.

499 Probiotic bacteria have a positive effect on iron absorption. However, the chemical
500 mechanisms of this influence are not understood. In fact, different international organizations
501 have recently concluded that there is insufficient evidence to claim a probiotic can help boost
502 iron absorption.

503 We demonstrate how and why probiotic bacteria increase iron absorption. We demonstrate
504 that *L. fermentum*, one of the main probiotics of the microbiota, exhibits an extraordinary ferric-
505 reducing activity and that this activity is mainly due to one of the molecules excreted by this
506 bacterium: p-hydroxyphenyllactic acid (HPLA). Because reduction of Fe(III) to Fe(II) is an
507 essential step for iron absorption in the gastrointestinal tract, HPLA reduction of Fe(III) can
508 boost Fe(II) absorption through the DMT1 channels of enterocytes. An in vitro experiment has
509 been done to confirm this hypothesis.

510 This discovery opens new avenues for the treatment of human iron deficiency, one of the most
511 common and widespread nutritional disorders in the world.

512

ACCEPTED MANUSCRIPT

25

**Identification of the Key Excreted Molecule by *Lactobacillus fermentum*
Related to Host Iron Absorption**

**Ana González¹, Natividad Gálvez¹, Jesús Martín², Fernando Reyes², Ignacio Pérez-
Victoria^{2,*}, Jose M. Dominguez-Vera^{1,*}**

Figure S1. ¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CD₃OD) of the final pooled fractions displaying ferric-reducing activity.

Figure S2. Expansion of the ^1H NMR spectrum of the final pooled fractions displaying ferric-reducing activity, highlighting the signals of HPLA.

Figure S3. Comparison of the ¹H NMR spectra of the final pooled fractions displaying ferric-reducing activity (red) and the HPLA standard (blue).

Figure S4. Expansion of the ^1H NMR spectra of the final pooled fractions displaying ferric-reducing activity (red) and the HPLA standard (blue).

Figure S5. Expansion of the COSY spectrum of the final pooled fractions displaying ferric-reducing activity showing the key correlations for HPLA.

Figure S6. Expansion of the HSQC spectrum of the final pooled fractions displaying ferric-reducing activity showing the cross peaks of HPLA.

Figure S7. HSQC spectrum of the HPLA standard.

Figure S8. Expansion of the HMBC spectrum of the final pooled fractions displaying ferric-reducing activity showing key correlations for HPLA.

Table S1. NMR Spectroscopic Data (500 MHz, CD₃OD, at 24 °C) for HPLA

position	δ_{H} (<i>J</i> in Hz)	δ_{C} , type
1	-	n. d. , C
2	4.25, dd (7.7, 4.5)	72.7, CH
3	a 2.99, dd (14.0, 4.4) b 2.80, dd (14.0, 7.8)	40.4, CH ₂
1'	-	129.8, C
2'	7.07, d (8.5)	131.3, CH
3'	6.69, d (8.5)	115.7, CH
4'	-	156.8, C

Figure S8. LC-UV-HRMS analysis of the final pooled fractions displaying ferric-reducing activity showing detection of a major component matching the molecular formula of HPLA.